

Performance Improvement of Directly Modulated VCSEL-based BVT via Optical SSB Filter and Time-Delay Neural Network

Mumtaz Ali, Michela Svaluto Moreolo, Laia Nadal, Francisco Javier Vílchez, and Josep Maria Fàbrega
Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA),
Av. Carl Friedrich Gauss 7, 08860 Castelldefels, Spain
emails: {mali, michela.svaluto, laia.nadal, javier.vilchez, jmfabrega}@cttc.es

Abstract—In the rapidly evolving landscape of optical fiber communication, achieving high performances in short to long reach transmission systems is paramount. Particularly, for addressing the challenges posed by future networks, bandwidth/bitrate variable transceiver (BVT) based on directly modulated (DM) vertical cavity surface-emitting lasers (VCSELs) represents an attractive and efficient solution. This paper presents an approach that combines optical single sideband (SSB) filtering at the transmitter and time delay neural network (TDNN) at the receiver to enhance the performance of VCSEL-based BVT. We investigated the effects of DM VCSELs' chirp characteristics on signal integrity. By using its ability to represent complex time-varying signals, the proposed TDNN successfully compensates for the inherent chirp in DM VCSELs, improving signal quality and lowering bit error rates (BERs). Using an optical SSB filter simultaneously reduces the effects of chromatic dispersion. Our results demonstrate that the combination of a 20 GHz bandwidth SSB filter and a trained TDNN model with a correlation coefficient of 0.9875 provides capacities in the 80–53 Gb/s range, at the BER of $4.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$, for short-to-medium-reach transmission networks with fiber lengths up to 40 km.

Index Terms—bandwidth/bitrate variable transceiver, neural network, optical single sideband filter, vertical-cavity surface-emitting laser.

I. INTRODUCTION

As global data consumption increases, the demand for high-speed, reliable optical communication systems has reached unprecedented levels [1], [2]. Vertical-cavity surface-emitting lasers (VCSELs) for bandwidth/bitrate variable transceiver (BVT) have emerged as promising candidates for high-capacity optical networks due to their compact form factor, low power consumption, and ease of integration into existing fiber optic systems [3]. However, the direct modulation of VCSELs poses significant challenges, including chirp and sensitivity to chromatic dispersion (CD), which can adversely affect the signal quality depending on the target reach and different communication scenarios [4]–[6].

To address the challenges of nonlinear behaviour in optical communication systems, researchers are increasingly turning from traditional model-based designs techniques to machine learning (ML) techniques, particularly end-to-end (E2E) learning with deep learning [7]. With the evolving role of E2E

learning, the performance of optical interconnects is evaluated for the VCSEL or DM laser based optical systems that are critical for short-reach applications [8], [9]. In [8], a framework for optimising DM lasers based on E2E learning is proposed, showing that system performance is enhanced by jointly optimising transmitter and receiver DSP parameters. A comprehensive review of ML-based VCSEL modelling is given in [9], with a focus on how effectively it can adjust to changing operating conditions and reduce transmission impairments. The unifying theme across these studies is that the E2E learning offers a powerful tool for holistic optimization while highlighted the challenges of model accuracy, compliance with standards, and handling VCSEL-based optical system variability. A nonlinear model based on the Hammerstein-Wiener system is discussed in [10] for chirp compensation in DM VCSEL-based BVTs, incorporating a phase modulator and an adaptive DSP. Although it increases system complexity, this method increases transmission reach and reduces OSNR needs by 4 dB.

In [11], the spiking neural networks (SNNs) is used for nonlinear demapping at the receiver side of an intensity-modulation direct-detection (DD) optical links transmitting at the bit rate of 200 Gb/s. In the implementation, SNNs outperform traditional linear and nonlinear equalization methods, including Volterra nonlinear equalization and artificial neural networks. In [12], a silicon photonic neural network (PNN) based on time delay neural network principle is used to mitigate chromatic dispersion in optical fiber links. A 4-channel time-delayed complex perceptron as a PNN device is tested with 10 Gb/s non-return-to-zero optical signals over distances up to 125 km. The PNN device optimizes a separation-loss function during the learning phase to maximize the separation of transmitted 0s and 1s, thereby improving the bit-error-rate (BER). The results show improvements in both performance and ease of use compared to traditional methods. The PNN device's on-chip equalization reduces power consumption and latency, offering a promising alternative to digital signal processing (DSP) techniques.

In [7], the authors explore the application of ML to enhance DSP for nonlinear optical communications. Traditional methods like digital back propagation (DBP) face challenges due to complex interactions between Kerr nonlinearity, CD,

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Fig. 1. VCSEL-based BVT model.

and amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise. The authors propose an optimized DBP modeled as a deep neural network (DNN), which interleaves linear and nonlinear operations to improve performance. This approach is tested in both single-channel and polarization division multiplexed wavelength division multiplexed systems, showing significant performance gains over conventional DSP algorithms. The DNN-based DBP not only enhances transmission performance but also provides insights into the noise statistics of fiber nonlinearity compensation. The study reveals that ASE noise and incomplete CD compensation introduce distortions that accumulate along DBP stages, necessitating a balance between suppressing these distortions and inverting fiber propagation effects. This work demonstrates how ML can complement human analytical thinking, advancing both theoretical understanding and practical performance in optical communications.

In [13], a Time-Delay Neural Network (TDNN) is implemented for its ability to effectively learn the temporal dynamics of signals, which is crucial for coherent optical orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) systems. Unlike recurrent neural networks and long short-term memory networks, which have complex training processes, TDNNs use feedforward structures that simplify and accelerate training. By incorporating time-delay terms, TDNNs can extend the input of feedforward neural networks to include past information, enabling them to better capture the time-domain properties of signals. This results in significant benefits, including improved peak-to-average power ratio reduction, enhanced BER performance, and extended transmission distances.

Furthermore, the implementation of optical single sideband (SSB) filtering presents a viable solution to mitigate the effects of chromatic dispersion in long-haul transmissions. The SSB filtering effectively eliminates one sideband of the optical signal, thus enhancing spectral efficiency and minimizing dispersion-related signal degradation [14]. This technique is crucial for extending the reach of optical communication links without requiring additional amplification, making it particularly advantageous in metropolitan and long-distance networks.

This paper proposes an integration of TDNN and SSB

filtering to enhance the performance of VCSEL-based BVTs. By combining these advanced techniques, it is possible to improve signal quality and adaptability against VCSEL-induced distortions and chromatic dispersion effects. The effectiveness of the TDNN in mitigating VCSEL non-linearities is explored alongside the SSB filtering, providing a comprehensive approach to optimize long-reach optical transmission.

The paper is structured as follows. In section II, an overview of the adaptive DSP for OFDM-based digital signal generation and modulation is presented using the VCSEL-based BVT model. The BVT transmitter (BVTx) and receiver (BVRx) side front-end components are subsequently explained. The TDNN model is introduced in section III. Considering the BVT model with SSB filter and TDNN, section IV provides the performance evaluation of transmission capacities over different standard single mode fiber (SSMF) reach. Section V concludes the paper indicating future work directions.

II. BVT SYSTEM MODEL

Figure 1 shows the VCSEL-based BVT model including different BVTx and BVRx components, as well as the blocks of optical SSB filter and SSMF. The DSP employs adaptive loading based on OFDM modulation at the BVTx for increased adaptability and flexibility. Using the Levin Campello (LC) approach, adaptive loading allows for the flexible application of different modulation schemes and power levels to the OFDM subcarrier (SC) based on the estimated SNR of the SCs for a given channel [14]. The mapper dynamically assigns the appropriate bit number to each SC using an optimal bit loading method. All the OFDM SCs (here we consider 512) are loaded using the LC approach with appropriate bits per symbol based on the estimated SNR obtained from the channel state information. Based on the amount of OFDM SCs used, the LC-based approach allows for fine-grained spectrum manipulation with a resolution of tens of MHz. For instance, the granularity that results from employing 512 SCs with 20 GHz of bandwidth is around 39 MHz. Data mapping and parallelisation, training symbol (TS) insertion, inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) implementation, cyclic prefix (CP) insertion, serialisation, and radio frequency (RF) up-conversion are the DSP functions that

generate an OFDM signal, as shown in the Fig. 1 inset. A digital-to-analog converter (DAC) is then used to transform the OFDM signal from digital to analog. The BVTx front-end uses DM-VCSEL to transform the analog RF signal into an optical signal. The operating point of the DM-VCSEL is determined by the constant bias current. The DM VCSEL model predicts the modulation dynamics of commercially available VCSELS by describing the interactions between carrier density, photon density, optical phase, and temperature using the VCSEL rate equations [6], [15]. Based on the solution to DM VCSEL rate equations for output power $P(t)$ and frequency chirp $\Delta\nu(t)$ [10], the fluctuations in $\Delta\nu(t)$ over time can be approximated as [5],

$$\Delta\nu(t) = \frac{\alpha}{4\pi} \left(\frac{1}{P} \frac{dP}{dt} + \kappa P \right)$$

where the first term indicates the transient chirp, and the second term is the adiabatic chirp.

The BVTx output is a DSB signal, and to reduce the effects of CD, an optical SSB filter is used in the optical domain before transmission over SSMF [16], [17]. By selectively eliminating one sideband, an optical SSB filter reduces dispersion-related impairments in optical fibers and allows the system to use a smaller bandwidth. To mathematically represent the DSB signal and SSB filtering process [18], consider an optical field $E(t)$ generated by the DM VCSEL:

$$E(t) = A_c e^{j\omega_c t} + A_m \cos(\omega_m t) e^{j\omega_c t},$$

where A_c is the carrier amplitude, ω_c is the angular frequency of the carrier, A_m is the OFDM signal modulation amplitude, and ω_m is the OFDM signal modulation angular frequency. The term $A_m \cos(\omega_m t) e^{j\omega_c t}$ represents the DSB modulation by OFDM signal, which expands to:

$$E(t) = A_c e^{j\omega_c t} + \frac{A_m}{2} \left(e^{j(\omega_c + \omega_m)t} + e^{j(\omega_c - \omega_m)t} \right).$$

The output of the optical SSB filter with one sideband can be written as,

$$E_{SSB}(t) = A_c e^{j\omega_c t} + \frac{A_m}{2} e^{j(\omega_c + \omega_m)t}.$$

The optical signal $E_{SSB}(t)$ is received at the Rx frontend using the cost-effective DD scheme after propagating across the SSMF channel. The DD scheme's main elements are a PIN photodetector, a transimpedance amplifier (TIA), also an EDFA, and an ASE noise filter can be considered. The analog-to-digital converter (ADC) digitises the signal, which is fed to the trained TDNN block. By using the detected signal, the TDNN minimises the chirp effects caused by the DM VCSEL. This improves overall signal integrity and enables reliable data transmission by producing a corrected output signal from TDNN that has a reduced chirp. Finally, the transmitted data is retrieved using the DSP Rx. The DSP Rx performs the following functions: down conversion of the RF signal, data parallelisation, CP removal, fast Fourier transform (FFT), equalisation, symbol demapping, and serialisation.

III. TIME DELAY NEURAL NETWORK MODEL

A TDNN is used to model the relationship between the DAC input as an output y and ADC output as an input x . Given a sequence $x = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T]$ of length T , the TDNN layer applies temporal convolutions over the input sequence [19]. For an input sequence $x(t)$ at time step t , the output of the convolution operation in the first TDNN layer $h^{(1)}(t)$ can be given by:

$$h^{(1)}(t) = \sigma \left(\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} w_k \cdot x(t-k) + b \right),$$

where K is the kernel (or context window) size, w_k are the weights of the convolution filter, b is a bias term, σ is the activation function. The convolution operation here takes into account K previous time steps for each output, enabling the model to learn dependencies up to K -steps back.

TDNNs typically consist of multiple layers stacked together. For an l -layer TDNN, the output of layer l is a function of the output of the previous layer $l-1$ is given as

$$h^{(l)}(t) = \sigma \left(\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} w_k^{(l)} \cdot h^{(l-1)}(t-k) + b^{(l)} \right).$$

The final output of the TDNN, after L layers, provides the prediction for each timestep $y(t)$, which will be the DAC input signal sequence. The final output is typically a linear transformation of the last layer output

$$y(t) = W_{out} \cdot h^{(L)}(t) + b_{out},$$

where W_{out} and b_{out} are the weights and bias for the output layer.

In order to optimise the network's parameters for accurate time-dependent predictions, the TDNN model is trained through a sequence of repetitive processes. The following subsections discuss in detail about the four primary phases of this process: forward propagation, loss computation, backward propagation, and gradient descent update.

A. Forward Propagation

In this first stage, the model generates predictions, $\hat{y}(t)$, for each timestep t , by performing forward propagation via the TDNN layers. Using temporal relationships and identifying patterns across timesteps, the model sequentially processes incoming data. At each timestep, this approach yields an output that shows the target variable's estimate from the model.

B. Loss Calculation

The next step is to measure the prediction error once predictions have been created. The difference between the true target values $y(t)$ and the predicted values $\hat{y}(t)$ is known as the mean squared error, or MSE. The MSE loss function is expressed in the form for a series of predictions $\hat{y}(t)$ and ground truth $y(t)$ as

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (y(t) - \hat{y}(t))^2.$$

C. Backward Propagation

The model starts backpropagation through time (BPTT), an extension of backpropagation customised for sequential models, after calculating the loss. In order to determine the gradients of the loss in relation to each network weight, BPTT iteratively goes through each timestep. This procedure enables the model to evaluate the contribution of each parameter to the error, building up gradients over timesteps to give a comprehensive view of each parameter's effects.

D. Gradient Descent Update

Lastly, to minimise the computed loss, the model adjusts its parameters via gradient descent. By iteratively adapting the model's weights in the direction that minimises the loss, a particular optimisation approach improves the model. The model steadily improves its predictions through these updates, convergently reaching a desirable set of parameters.

When combined, these steps allow the TDNN model to learn patterns in the data in an adaptive manner, decreasing prediction errors with each iteration and gradually increasing the model's accuracy throughout training. The procedures of the TDNN system training are shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 TDNN model forward and training procedure

Input: Input sequence $x = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T]$, parameters $\{W^{(l)}, b^{(l)}\}$

Output: Predicted output \hat{y} , and trained weights W_{out} and biases b_{out}

- 1: Initialize $h^{(0)} = x$
 - 2: **for** each layer $l = 1$ to L **do**
 - 3: **for** each time step $t = 1$ to T **do**
 - 4: $h^l(t) \leftarrow \sigma \left(\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} w_k^l \cdot h^{l-1}(t-k) + b^l \right)$
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: **end for**
 - 7: Compute output \hat{y} using the final layer activations
 - 8: Compute MSE
 - 9: Backpropagate error and update weight w_k^l and bias b^l using gradient descent
 - 10: **return** \hat{y}
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IV. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF BVT MODEL WITH SSB FILTER AND TDNN

We have analysed the performance of BVTx and BVRx targeting different applications and network segments with focus on low cost BVT solutions. To reduce the chirp effect, we proposed TDNN and analysed the system performance. According to our previous experimental assessments [4], [14], [16], we utilised the capabilities of tailored experimental adaptive DSP blocks of BVT with integrated TDNN methods. For the numerical simulations, the parameters of different BVT elements are given in Table I.

The TDNN model was customized and trained using Bayesian regularisation, which restricts the squared values of parameters to reduce the effective number of parameters. By

TABLE I
BVT MODEL PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
No. of OFDM SCs	512
CP overhead	4%
TS overhead	1.9%
Target bit error rate	4.62×10^{-3}
Sampling Rate	64 GHz
VCSEL Bandwidth	20 GHz
VCSEL Bias Current, Optical Power	7.87 mA, 0.5 mW
Modulating Current, I_{mod}	6 mA
Max. RF Signal, $u(t)$	150 mVp-p
Optical SSB Filter Bandwidth	20 GHz
SSMF Length, Attenuation	0 to 80 km, 0.23 dB/km
SSMF Dispersion, Slope	17.5 ps/nm-km, 0.057 ps/nm ² -km
Chirp parameters, α, κ	3, 12 GHz/mW
EDFA Max. Gain, Noise Figure	20 dB, 4.7 dB
ASE Filter Bandwidth	30 GHz
PIN Responsivity, Dark Current, Noise Spectral Density	0.7 A/W, 1×10^{-9} A, 16×10^{-12} A/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$
Timesteps in TDNN Dataset	167040
TDNN Layer Size and Time Delay	10 and 8
Training Algorithm	Bayesian regularization
Performance Metric	Mean squared error
Maximum Epochs	1000
Gradient Threshold	1×10^{-7}
Mu (Damping Factor) target value	1×10^{10}

keeping the model's complexity to a minimum, this regularisation strategy successfully lowers the risk of overfitting, which is beneficial when working with smaller datasets or noisy data. The training performance indicator is MSE, a widely used regression task loss function that restricts large prediction errors significantly. Algorithm 2 presents the customized TDNN model training with Bayesian regularisation for the BVT time sequence. The achieved model's MSE for the training dataset is 5.93, indicating a low average prediction error. A strong linear relationship between the predicted and actual values is indicated by the training set's correlation coefficient (R), which is 0.9876. The R value in the test set remained high at 0.9875, but the MSE is a bit higher at 5.99. These results indicate that there is little overfitting and that the model generalised well to the test data.

The plots of the evaluated performances of chirped DSB and SSB signal transmissions with and without TDNN are shown in Fig. 2. For back-to-back (B2B) BVT, the DSB signal transmission capacity is 74 Gb/s in the absence of chirp. The CD effects cause the maximum B2B BVT capacity reduction to 54 Gb/s and 26 Gb/s for SSMF lengths of 40 km and 80 km, respectively. The DSB signal transmission capacity is decreased to 49 Gb/s for B2B when chirp is present. Interestingly, the capacity reduction slope in this scenario is the same as in the case of DSB without chirp for a maximum reach of 40 km. Because of the interaction between chirp and CD, the DSB with chirp curve slope decreases and the capacity reduction is slower for SSMF lengths greater than 40 km. With the TDNN-based chirp compensation, the achieved capacity is 56 Gb/s for B2B BVT. For 40 and 80 km SSMF lengths,

Algorithm 2 Customized TDNN model training with Bayesian regularization for BVT time sequence prediction

Input: Time sequence data x , time delay $T = 8$, hidden layer neurons $N = 10$

Output: Predicted output \hat{y} values with minimized overfitting

- 1: **Initialize** TDNN model with a single hidden layer of N neurons
- 2: **Set** Bayesian regularization parameters
- 3: **for** each epoch until convergence **do**
- 4: Extract temporal features using time delay T
- 5: Forward propagate the input data x through the TDNN
- 6: Compute predicted output \hat{y}
- 7: Calculate MSE between predicted and actual values
- 8: Use Bayesian regularisation to adjust biases and weights.
- 9: Adjust model parameters to reduce the amount of regularised error.
- 10: Track the number of parameters that are effective.
- 11: **end for**
- 12: Analyse the model's performance using test and training datasets.
- 13: Compute R values and compare MSE for both datasets
- 14: **if** Training and test sets' MSE values closely match each other. **then**
- 15: Confirm minimal overfitting
- 16: **end if**
- 17: **return** Measures of performance and the final trained TDNN model

Fig. 2. Performance of DSB and SSB signal transmission with DD in VCSEL-based BVT System.

similar capacities of 29 and 23 Gb/s are achieved as in the DSB with chirp case.

With the SSB filter, the chirp-free B2B BVT capacity is 74 Gb/s which is similar to that of B2B BVT with DSB without chirp case. We have a slightly higher capacity of 56.4 Gb/s for a 40 km reach since the SSB filter provides

a tolerance to CD. For 80 km reach, the capacity is reduced to 28 Gb/s. When compared to DSB with chirp case for B2B BVT, the capacity in SSB with chirp case indicates a benefit of additional 15 Gb/s. Even SSB transmission is more resilient to CD effects, it utilises less power, which results in a steeper capacity loss slope up to a 40 km reach. Additionally, in SSB signal transmission between 40 and 80 km, no CD and chirp interaction is observed. The SSB with chirp and TDNN case demonstrated its effectiveness against CD and chirp by achieving the maximum capacities which are 80 Gb/s in B2B, 53 Gb/s at 40 km, and 28 Gb/s at 80 km. Notably, due to the SSB filter's ability to reduce CD effects and the TDNN's limited tolerance for chirp, the capacity of SSB with chirp and TDNN is higher than that of SSB without chirp for up to 25 km reach. However, SSB without chirp has a capacity of up to 2.5 Gb/s higher than SSB with chirp and TDNN for distances above 25 km. This is because, when CD and chirp do not interact (since the SSB filter reduces the effects of CD), the residual chirp in the SSB with chirp and TDNN case effects TDNN performance, which causes a slight reduction in system performance at longer distances.

When TDNN implementations are compared in DSB and SSB signal transmissions, considering chirp and SSB option provides a significantly higher BVT capacity (80 Gb/s) than DSB (56 Gb/s). Both BVT signal transmission capacities decrease with the increase of the fiber length, although SSB continuously outperforms DSB in terms of capacity.

In comparison to [7], our results agree with ML-based optical signal processing, where deep learning frameworks—like DBP based on DNNs—have outperformed conventional model-based compensation methods. This knowledge guided the development of our TDNN-based receiver, which uses adaptive learning to reduce CD and VCSEL chirp without the need for parameter tuning. For DM VCSEL-based BVT systems, this method provides a more scalable and useful solution by enabling increased transmission capacity and decreased system complexity [10]. Furthermore, this offers a feasible alternative for ML techniques, allowing for improved transmission performance without requiring a lot of data-driven training [8], [9]. The improved capacity increases support the effectiveness of our method and support research on chirp and dispersion mitigation techniques in VCSEL-based optical communication systems.

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that DM VCSEL-based BVTs can be an important enabler for improving the effectiveness and performance of optical communication systems over short-to-medium reach lengths. Using a Bayesian-regularized TDNN together with an optical SSB filter, we enable to significantly increase transmission capacity and reliability across fiber lengths of up to 40 km.

This VCSEL-based BVT system will be expanded in future research to meet the growing demands of increased data rates and long-haul communication. In particular, we will further study the proposed BVT-based transmission system

implementation to enable effective performance improvement also over longer reach. In order to create a more effective and scalable network infrastructure, the combination of optical and machine learning approaches provides a viable framework for next high-capacity optical communication systems. Additional research objectives include improving Bayesian regularisation for larger and complex data sets.

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